

APPLICATION OF MULTIPARAMETRIC ECHOGRAPHY IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF CYSTS AND TUMOR-LIKE FORMATIONS OF THE OVARIES IN GIRLS (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *Cysts and appendageal formations are uncommon in girls. However, when they occur, they cause concern for both the patient and her family. Many physicians are unfamiliar with the proper treatment for these appendageal formations and quickly resort to surgical intervention. It is estimated that the incidence of cysts and appendageal formations is approximately 2.6 per 100,000 girls under the age of 18 years [1,6,14]. It is estimated that 10% of ovarian formations in girls turn out to be malignant [3,5]. Malignant ovarian neoplasms account for only one percent of all malignant neoplasms found in patients under the age of 15 years [2,5].*

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Although the detection of ovarian cysts and formations in girls causes concern, conservative treatment is justified as most of these tumors are benign [7,11]. It is important to understand the features of the manifestation, assessment, and treatment of benign ovarian cysts in order to preserve ovarian function.

The diagnosis can be more difficult, even delayed or missed due to a low index of suspicion, nonspecific complaints, or the consideration of more common acute abdominal processes that mimic appendage problems. This article will discuss the imaging options and characteristics of appendageal lesions, including neoplasms, vascular disorders, infections, and some important paraovarian mimics in pediatric patients [6,13].

The preferred method for initial visualization of the female pelvis remains grayscale ultrasound with additional color and pulsed-wave Doppler imaging. Ultrasound is safe, inexpensive, and does not involve ionizing radiation. When the patient's bladder is distended, it creates an ultrasound window, allowing the identification of the ovaries in most cases.

Tumor-like ovarian formations have various ultrasound characteristics [8]. Some cystic formations may be complex cysts with detachment, hemorrhage, or thick walls. Differential diagnosis between tumor-like, benign, and malignant ovarian lesions is quite challenging, and transabdominal ultrasound becomes the primary imaging tool for girls [8,9]. According to the classification by the International Ovarian Tumor Analysis Group, multilocular cysts with a solid component have the highest risk of malignancy [14]. Multiparametric ultrasound allows for a more accurate differential diagnosis between tumor-like, benign, and malignant formations.

Ovaries may be particularly noticeable in newborn girls due to the prolonged presence of maternal hormones, and small follicles are often seen even in prepubertal girls. The typical average ovarian volume is about 1 cm³ in girls under 5 years old; the ovaries double in size by age 12 [1,5,8]. During puberty, the ovaries grow to approximately 4 cm³ in size [2,7,10], paralleling the

growth of the uterus. When lesions are detected, the ultrasound specialist collects information about the size and internal characteristics of the lesions, as well as the presence and quality of vascular blood flow.

If further imaging evaluation is required, both CT and MRI are available and offer specific advantages. MRI, like ultrasound, does not involve ionizing radiation. It also provides excellent soft tissue contrast, including dynamic enhancement for assessing vessel integrity. However, MRI takes longer and may require sedation, making it more labor-intensive in emergency situations. Thus, CT remains crucial due to its speed, spatial resolution, and ability to globally assess the abdominal and pelvic regions, especially for planning surgical interventions. It can help exclude mimics of appendage anomalies and diseases and determine the stage of malignant neoplasms [6, 12].

The most common appendage pathology in the pediatric population is ovarian cysts. Ovarian cysts are the most frequent cause of abdominal masses in fetuses and newborns [2,5,9,12]. An anechoic focus in the ovary is considered a follicle if its size is less than 3.0 cm. A mature dominant follicle may not develop properly and can grow into a functional cyst or corpus luteum. Rupture or hemorrhage often leads to these patients seeking medical attention. Depending on the degree of complexity, associated with blood products, clot formation, lysis, and retraction, the appearance varies with all cross-sectional imaging methods.

Regardless of whether they are simple or complex, these lesions are evaluated using ultrasound to confirm resolution and exclude cystic neoplasms.

Tumor-like ovarian formations typically have a cystic component and can be benign or malignant. The solid component is the most statistically significant predictor of malignancy [1,5,8,12]. Categories are determined by cell origin: germ cell tumors, epithelial tumors, and stromal tumors. These neoplasms typically occur in postpubertal girls, causing pain, abdominal distention, and symptoms related to hormonal effects when the formations are functioning.

The first category of neoplasms is germ cell tumors. Benign teratomas account for 67% of pediatric ovarian neoplasms, and in 25% of cases, they are bilateral [5, 7, 10]. Mature teratomas contain tissues from all three primitive germ layers—endoderm, mesoderm, and ectoderm. The presence of fat or calcification in the lesion is diagnostic and can be easily recognized through CT or MRI. Diagnosis can be slightly more challenging with ultrasound, but several signs are helpful, including the "iceberg sign" (a coarse, shadowing calcification), the dermoid mesh (linear borders representing hair), and the dermoid plug (a hyperechoic nodule with fat, hair, and teeth). Some teratomas contain immature elements and have the potential for recurrence and metastasis. This subtype can even be present in infants and may lead to peritoneal disease spread. Chemotherapy can cause maturation of implants into a benign form, despite the persistent size [4, 6].

Other categories of germ cell tumors include dysgerminomas, yolk sac tumors, choriocarcinomas, and mixed varieties [3, 7, 16]. These tumors are indistinguishable on imaging, but imaging characteristics determine the surgical approach and provide preoperative staging. Final diagnosis and staging are the prerogative of pathology.

The second category of neoplasms includes epithelial tumors—cystadenomas and cystadenocarcinomas. Most tumors in this category are divided into serous and mucinous subtypes, both of which tend to be quite large at the time of detection. On imaging, internal septations, papillary projections, and/or larger solid components are identified. On ultrasound, mucinous tumors may have weak internal echogenic signals from the mucosa. The overall malignancy rate

ranges from 7.5% to 30% [4, 8]. Imaging descriptions consider the likelihood of malignancy, vascularization of the lesion, ovarian origin, and signs of lesion rupture. The uterus is typically tilted toward the tumor's origin [9, 11, 15, 18].

The third category of primary neoplasms is stromal tumors. These include granulosa-theca cell tumors, fibromas, thecomas, Sertoli-Leydig cell tumors, and undifferentiated stromal tumors of the sex cord. Many of these tumors are hormonally active and, as a result, appear earlier than those without hormonal function [6, 10, 11, 15]. Typically, these tumors are solid, unilateral, and encapsulated. They may resemble germ cell tumors without fat and calcium, but their appearance may indicate a cellular origin.

Other rare ovarian neoplasms range from aggressive malignant tumors, such as small cell carcinoma (usually associated with hypercalcemia), to benign lesions like hemangiomas. Metastatic disease can also affect the ovaries due to hematogenous or contiguous spread. This group of malignant neoplasms includes adenocarcinoma of the colon, Burkitt's lymphoma, alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma, Wilms' tumor, neuroblastoma, and retinoblastoma [6, 11, 15].

Any ovarian or fallopian tube neoplasm predisposes the patient to ovarian torsion. Of course, ovarian torsion can also occur without a lesion due to excessive mobility of the ovary or fallopian tube.

Ovarian torsion is a critical diagnosis in any situation and requires urgent surgical intervention. Diagnosis can be particularly challenging if the torsion is intermittent. The most important sign is an enlarged, round ovary compared to the contralateral side. Follicles often migrate to the periphery, a characteristic known as the "pearl string sign" [12, 14, 18]. Since a normal Doppler study cannot rule out early or intermittent torsion during the examination, abnormal ovarian morphology raises suspicion of intermittent torsion. Poor vascular flow or an obvious absence of blood flow on ultrasound without morphological changes is not definitive. For pediatric patients, transabdominal ultrasound with an extended bladder is a comprehensive examination. If advanced imaging is needed, MRI without or with contrast can confirm the diagnosis and reveal any underlying lesions. Torsion can occur in utero, and a nonviable ovary in an infant may appear as a complex cystic and solid mass without vascular flow, later developing into a small calcified mass visible on X-rays. Ovarian torsion in infants may occur in the abdominal cavity rather than the pelvis.

Another urgent condition involving the adnexa in postpubertal girls is ectopic pregnancy, highlighting the importance of a pregnancy test in clinical assessment. Any complex adnexal mass in the absence of an intrauterine pregnancy and with a positive pregnancy test raises serious concern. The presence of complex ascites complicates the situation. Risk factors include pelvic inflammatory disease, previous ectopic pregnancy, intrauterine devices, in vitro fertilization, and tubal surgery [13, 15].

Infection of the pelvic organs can originate from the adnexa or affect adjacent structures, creating a visual appearance similar to neoplasms with complicating features such as torsion or ectopic pregnancy. Classic imaging findings of tubo-ovarian abscesses and pyosalpinges show complex fluid collections with thick walls and enhanced borders or increased peripheral vascular flow, often accompanied by adjacent inflammatory changes and free fluid. Ultrasound is effective for detecting septations, but CT and MRI provide a global assessment, which is often necessary before surgery [8, 10, 14, 18]. CT and MRI also perform better than ultrasound in ruling out appendicitis, a much more common diagnosis in this patient population, as well as phlegmon or

abscess associated with inflammatory bowel disease. It is important to note that Crohn's disease without an abscess should not be treated surgically, so a correct diagnosis significantly influences treatment decisions.

Thus, the key clinical issues for a radiologist when dealing with adnexal lesions in girls are the site of origin, differential diagnosis of cysts, and distinguishing between benign and malignant formations. The combination of clinical presentation and imaging results will determine the appropriate treatment, whether it involves conservative management followed by surgical intervention. Ultrasound remains the "workhorse" for detecting and diagnosing cysts and ovarian masses in girls, while CT and MRI provide additional information when more detailed diagnostics are needed.

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